

**Stylistic Analysis in Daud Kamal’s “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” and
“*Erasure*”**

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Abstract

The research is concerned with the stylistic analysis of the two poems of Daud Kamal, "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". The stylistic approach is employed to find out language features in both poems and expose the meaning of the poems based on the language elements. This study addresses two research issues: how language features are used in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*," and how language aspects reveal the meaning of the poems. The first problem has been answered using Paul Simpson's theory of language levels (2004). The poems were examined on four different levels of language: phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic. The second issue was answered by relating language features to the meaning they contain. The findings in this study are Alliteration, consonance, assonance, and rhyme schemes are used to point out particular words at the phonological level. The researcher concentrates on capitalization and punctuation such as commas, dashes, and ellipses at the graphological level. On the grammatical level, the present tense used is pointing out the poet's current circumstance. Figures of speech such as metaphor, simile, imagery, and symbol contain the meaning of the poems at the semantic level. Although both poems contain elements of memories, they express different meanings. The language elements in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" represent depression and hope, whereas the language features in "*Erasure*" indicate the poet's nostalgic feelings and the passage of time.

Keywords: Stylistic analysis, Language features, Memories, Erasure

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study:

Literary work is a kind of self-expression that uses words as the building blocks for ideas and pictures. According to Moddy, "Literature serves four purposes: 1) to develop four language skills; 2) to increase knowledge about aspects of human experience like tradition, culture, and religion, etc. It fosters character development in the readers or audience, encourages creativity and feeling, and supports character development" (1984, p. 5).

One of the literary genres is creative writing. The genres of poetry, short stories, and novels are examples of creative writing. As there are no restrictions on creative writing. Creative writing typically expresses the author's perspective on certain events, as in William Blake's poetry. The Industrial Revolution, which Blake once lived through, brought about a significant shift in history. Blake thought that the Industrial Revolution, however, did more harm than benefit. Children were made to work as slaves throughout the industrial revolution, and there was a lot of discrimination. Blake used his book "Songs of Experience," which is truthful in describing the suffering caused by the industrial revolution, to show his hate for that movement. The author's experiences are also reflected in literary works. One of the instances is William Carlos Williams's poetry "Red Wheelbarrow." William was a doctor in the region of New Jersey. One of his patients who have a terrible illness became an inspiration to him to write the poem.

To understand literary works better and to show authors some respect, it is essential to study them. Its style can be used to analyze literary works. The purpose of an author's writing style is to give the reader a specific meaning or interpretation. Wales defined style as "the perceived unique way of expressing oneself in writing or speech" (2011, p.397). However, style in linguistics refers to the manner an author or writer puts together the words in literary works. Style in linguistics emphasizes that the language of poetry has its qualities, including the possibility of flouting grammatical rules, a distinctive sound pattern, and special graphology.

To prevent the admiration of literary works from being solely dependent on presumption, stylistics in literary texts tries to demonstrate how language style can generate meanings (isti'adah, 2017). So, stylistic analysis is used to examine the literary works. Widdowson defines stylistics as the study of literary discourse with a linguistic focus (1975). Additionally, stylistics is defined as “the study of unique language use and the explanation of its function and impact” (Verdon, 2002, p.4). In a nutshell, stylistics is the scientific study of style. It is further said that “style leads to the structure, pattern, and arrangement of words to construct sentences in spoken or written form” (Leech, 1989).

The terms stylistics, language features, and poem are overburdened. The first of these terms is stylistics. Stylistics is defined as the linguistic study of style by Leech and Short (2007). As a result, stylistics can be defined as a branch of linguistics that studies the style of language text. The second term is "language features" which refers to any characteristic or distinguishing quality of spoken or written language as defined by linguistics (Crystal, 2008). As a result, the phrase "language features" can be used to refer to the characteristics of literary works. Phonology, graphology, morphology, syntax/grammar, lexical analysis, semantics, and pragmatics are the seven layers of language aspects that can be investigated, according to Simpson (2004, p.5). The distinctive meaning of a poem is created by the interaction of all linguistic aspects. Briefly put, linguistic features serve as a vehicle for authors to communicate the themes of their creative creations.

The poem is the third terminology. A poem is a piece of writing where the words are chosen not just for their evident meaning but also for the sounds and imagery they evoke. They are written in different lines, typically in a repetitive rhythm, and frequently at the end of the lines they rhyme. A poem is one of the literary works whose function is to serve as a representation of what is inside someone's thoughts as the poem is creative writing. A poem conveys specific ideas and messages from the author for the reader to understand. To conclude, stylistic is a structure-based linguistic examination of style and word arrangements to determine its aim and impact.

The researcher employs four language features of analysis in this study. This study aims to analyze the morphological, syntactical, graphological, and semantic levels of a poem and how

those features can be used to reveal the meaning of the poem. The poems studied in this study were written by Daud Kamal and were entitled “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” and “*Erasure*”.

Daud Kamal is a prolific Pakistani English poet whose sublime art went unnoticed for the majority of his life. Kamal's poetic art has an individualistic, one-of-a-kind, and distinct style. Its uniqueness stems from his method of writing it in fragments. Like Wordsworth, his major themes are rustic and pastoral. Kamal is considered one of the greatest mystic poets because his work primarily conveys Sufism. He focuses on spirituality, and mysticism and spiritual deadness are recurring themes in his work. Furthermore, as a rural poet, his poetry is rich in imagery, particularly natural imagery. His art is said to have been enchanted by world-renewed Imagists such as W.B. Yeats and Ezra Pound. His poetry has a distinct flavor of history and the past. He never fails to connect the past and the present. That is why his poetic art sometimes takes on a nostalgic tone as if the poet is missing something deadly.

The current study will analyze Daud Kamal's poems using linguistic features to reveal the poems' deeper meaning. As a result, this research employs a specific study as the theoretical foundation. This preliminary study employs a stylistic approach. The stylistic goal of this study is to demonstrate the language elements employed in the poem and to determine how those features are used to reveal the meaning of the poem.

1.2 Problem statement

Daud Kamal is one of Pakistan's most well-known poets, however, few people are familiar with his work, and finding his poetry volumes/collections is exceedingly challenging. This study aims to conduct original research on the poems written by Pakistani authors. The researcher plans to use stylistic analysis to evaluate the two poems of Daud Kamal. The study will highlight the four language levels used in the poem and expose the meaning of the two poems through those four levels of language.

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1.3 Research Objectives

Research objectives are given below,

1.3.1 Describing the language features used in the poems “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” and “*Erasure*” by Daud Kamal.

1.3.2 To analyze those language features used by Daud Kamal to reveal the meanings of the

poems “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” and “*Erasure*”.

1.4 Research Questions

Following are the research questions,

1. What is the language features used in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*" by Daud Kamal?
2. How do the meaning of the poems revealed from the use of language features?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The purpose of stylistics is not just to explain the formal elements of texts for their own sake, but to demonstrate how these elements are functional for understanding the text and connecting literary effects to linguistic grounds when relevant. Because stylistics is so closely related to human language, it also appeals to current readers and critics. Since research in this field has not been effectively done at the GGDC KDA Karak, it is hoped that this study will make its contribution by employing the stylistic technique in the analysis of two poems by Pakistani poet Daud Kamal that have not previously been researched and explored. The current study will increase readers' appreciation of poetry in general and Daud Kamal's poems on memories and hope for new coming in particular by supporting the meanings instinctively acquired through the use of stylistic elements. In summary, the study's findings may have a certain impact on linguistics and literary research because it may enlighten both students and other researchers about the importance of stylistics in their respective fields.

1.6 Delimitations

The researcher was limited to focusing on a specific topic because of the limited space and time available. As a result, two perspectives were used to define this study. At first, it only included selected poems by Daud Kamal, "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". Second, it was constrained from the theoretical framework's perspective. Scholars have proposed a variety of analysis, but the scope of this investigation was limited to the stylistic analysis. The stylistic approach is employed to find out language features in both poems and expose the meaning of the poems based on the language elements.

CHAPTER 2

Literature Review

A review of relevant studies and associated theories is covered in the following sub-chapters. A foundation for the analysis in the next chapters is provided by the review and theoretical material. In the overview of relevant studies, earlier studies by other stylistics experts are displayed to help explain why the current study is important. There will be a review of several relevant theories that are related to the subject. It will be explained how the theories and reviews helped to solve the problem of the current study.

A. Review of Relevant Studies

Other researchers' investigations have contributed to the current study in various ways. These investigations will aid the researcher in the development of concepts and in providing a deeper comprehension of the subject of the current study.

A research of Zahida Batool, Shumaila Kiran, and Mehmood Ahmad Azhar is titled "Stylistics Analysis of William Wordsworth's Poem "Daffodils." Three objectives are the main focus of this investigation. The poem's linguistic elements are first examined. The poet's use of language and its eventual impact on the reader's psyche are the next goals of the study. Four language levels, namely the graphological, phonological, morphological, and semantic levels, are used by the researcher to analyze language properties. Commas, semi-colons, and colons were discovered to provide pauses at the graphological level. Additionally, the poem uses foregrounding. At the phonological level, alliteration is used in the poem at several different places. Consonance, simile, personification (comparing daffodils to a crowd, etc.), metonymy, imagery, and onomatopoeia are examples of poetic devices that are discussed in the poem. A magnificent cluster of dancing daffodils by the lake serves as a metaphor for the poet's wonder at the semantic level, which is concerned with the meaning of words and sentences. Similarities and differences exist between the two investigations. The field of stylistics covered by this study is the same as that of the current study. A distinction is made in the examination of the poetry. The poems that were the subject of this study's analysis and the current study's analysis were both authored

by different poets. The examination of language aspects in the current study, however, is made easier by this work.

Another research project is "Stylistic Analysis of Robert Frost's Poem The Onset by Bari Khan, Raffique, and Siddique" (2014). This study includes two analyses. The study's initial goal is to examine the language elements in the poem "The Onset". Second, it seeks to clarify the poem's idea through its use of language, imagery, and sound effects. The study understands the fundamental concepts of good vs. evil, pessimism versus optimism, and life versus death. Since stylistics may be applied to literary texts, the researchers utilize a stylistic method to analyze the data. The researchers concentrate on using semantic and phonological levels to analyze the data. The first is poetic devices such as symbolism, imagery, simile, metaphor, and hyperbole. Alliteration, consonance, assonance, and rhyme scheme are among the sound devices that come in the second level.

The study's contribution to the current study is its interpretation of the poem's deeper significance. Frost employs symbols to represent thoughts obliquely at the semantic level. In the poem, "night" represents grief, "dark forests" represents the evil and mystique of existence, and "snow" represents death. In addition to visuals, the poem also uses language to convey a sense of experience. In the poem, Frost employs both metaphor and simile to make two analogies. Where a metaphor is a direct comparison, a simile is an indirect comparison. Last but not least, Frost exaggerates the truth of detail by using hyperbole. At the phonological level, alliteration, consonance, and assonance have been discovered to provide harmony in poetry. There are various rhyme schemes in the poem, one for each stanza. In conclusion, the poem "The Onset" is more than just a discussion of the seasons; it also contains deeper meaning regarding life and death. The diction, symbols, images, and metaphors all help to bring the poem's message to light.

The study and the current study are comparable to one another. Both studies use poetry as their source of data and stylistics as their method. In the analysis of the poetry, there is a distinction. The two poems, nevertheless, were written by two different poets, and this study only concentrates on two language features which are semantic and phonological levels, whereas the current study examines data from four language levels: phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic. Consequently, the current research advances the previous research.

A Stylistic Analysis of Maya Angelou's "Caged Bird" and "Still I Rise" is Xenia's study (2015). The researcher is focused on two distinct goals. The first is to explain which linguistic devices are used to advance the poems' subjects. The second is to identify the different linguistic devices utilized in each poem to develop the same theme—Black oppression and survival—by examining the language qualities that are used. Phonological, grammatical, lexical, and structural levels of language are the four levels of analysis used by the researcher. This study's analysis is what makes it useful for the current investigation. Rhyme and sound pattering are examples of language characteristics at the phonological level (alliteration, assonance, and consonance). The numbering of lines within stanzas is inconsistent on a graphological level. In both poems, the researcher finds a variety of repeated pronouns, word choices, metaphors, and similes, as well as different clauses, parallel structures, and preposterous phrases. As a consequence, the researcher discovers that both poems developed the same theme—black oppression and survival—using various linguistic devices.

Poems are used as the data and stylistics are used as the methodology in both Xenia's study and this one. The analysis of the poetry is where the difference is. While the current study attempts to examine the poem's meaning using language elements, Xenia's study looks for several language features that build the same theme. But Xenia's research aids the current study's analysis of language. "Maggie and Milly and Molly and May" by E.E. Cummings and "A Kite for Aibhin" by Seamus Heaney are both examined stylistically in Eman's research piece "A Stylistic Analysis of Two Selected Poems" (2014). Using a variety of linguistic methods, she analyzed the poetry to uncover explicit meanings to better understand the meaning and its interpretation. At the phonological level, the rhyming scheme found which is in "Maggie and Milly and Molly and May" is AABCDEFGGHH, and in the poem "A Kite for Aibhin", having various rhyming schemes, which is; (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, I, j....etc.). In the poem alliteration, assonance, consonance, and simile are also examined. The graphological deviation is also found in the analysis. This study is helpful in the current study in the analysis of language features.

Huma Iqbal, Sadaf Iqbal, and Aqsa Kanwal's research article, "Stylistic Analysis of The Poem "O Where are you Going" by W.H. Auden," was published in 2014. To further understand the poem, the researchers used a variety of linguistic approaches to study both its literal and implicit meanings. They concluded that Auden employs distinctive imagery to give illustrative

scenarios for the readers to comprehend and enjoy. Rabia Mahmood wrote a study titled "Stylistics Analysis of "Holly Thursday" by William Blake (2015). The study of Blake's poem "Holly Thursday" is conducted in this research article using a stylistics-based framework. The analysis of William Blake's poetry's structure and style is the focus of this research article. This study established the relationship between style and the diversity of ideas in literary texts.

Robert Frost's poem, "Stopping by Wood on a Snowy Evening" was the subject of stylistic analysis in the works of Muhammad Ahmad Hashmi, Muhammad Asim Mahmood, and Muhammad Ilyas Mahmood. Finding out the style of Robert Frost's poem "Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening" is the goal of this study. The scholars concentrate on the poem's use of linguistic devices. Those are the phonetic level, the phonological level, the graphitic level, and the lexico-syntactic level.

This study has two main goals. The first step is to identify the linguistic characteristics of Robert Frost's "Stopping by Woods in a Snowy Evening". The second step is to determine how the poem's theme is constructed using the language elements. The analysis is where this research contributes. Each word has been examined separately by the researcher on a phonetic, phonological, graphitic, lexico-syntactic, and grammatical level. Euphoric, cacophony, assonance, consonance, alliteration, rhyming scheme, tone, and modulation are among the phonetic factors the researcher examines. The researcher looked into Frost's writing style in graphitic. The researcher examined the words employed in the lexico-syntactic analysis. The researcher examines the figure of speech when denoting the poem.

In the last grammatical level, the researcher concentrated on the use of parts of speech like pronouns, nouns, verbs, and adjectives.

Since each word in the poem contains two syllables, the phonetic level of the poem's rhyme scheme is unique and uses assonance, consonance, and alliteration to create a pleasing and harmonic effect. The tone is changed to draw readers in and get them to concentrate on the images. Frost uses Anglo-Saxon vocabulary, which exhibits brevity and accuracy, together with polysemy (a natural layer) to choose his terms in the lexico-syntactic analysis. Finally, the use of antonyms like lovely-dark and woods-frozen lake is demonstrated by frost. Frost employs symbolism to reinforce the poem's meaning in the denotation. The village represents society and civilization,

while the woods, snow, and sleep represent nature and death, respectively. Frost also employs personification and metaphor in his writing. Last but not least, Frost frequently employs the first-person singular pronoun, demonstrating the author's intimate involvement with her life experiences. To demonstrate God's strength, he also employs the pronouns "He" and "His." Frost frequently employs a variety of nouns to distinguish between various images and symbols. The words in the poem are broken down into four categories: mental cognition verb, behavioral process verb, verbal process verb, and action verb. Finally, Frost combines a variety of stylistic approaches to give the poem a lyrical quality.

The poem's symbolism work to evoke a sense of death and sorrow by enhancing the dreadful tone and setting. Similarities and differences exist between this study and that of Hashmi. In terms of the data, both studies use poetry analysis as their primary source, although the author in each study is different. Both academic works examine the poem's linguistic elements. However, the Hashmi research seeks to understand the poem's content through the language and its linguistic characteristics. Meanwhile, in the current study, the researcher observes the goal of language elements in revealing the meaning of the poem. As a result, the studies varied in their use of linguistic elements and authors.

Capacity for comprehension of such literary works, but also plays a crucial role in language-based instruction for non-native speakers, enabling them to comprehend the target language that is easy. A study paper written by TIMUCIN from 2010 is titled "Exploring the Language of Poems: A Stylistic Study," and it examines numerous aspects about how significant stylistics are when analyzing a literary work. The stylistic approach not only improves the reader's for readers to understand.

The following study is a journal paper titled "Stylistic Analysis of the Poem "Hope is the Thing with Feathers" by Ali, Bhatti, and Shah (2016). The purpose of this study is to examine the poem "Hope is the Thing with Feathers" from a stylistic standpoint. The researcher analyzes the poetry on graphological, grammatical, phonological, and lexical levels while doing the research. On the graphological level, Dickinson utilizes capitalization to emphasize terms to highlight the poem's core theme: hope. They also discover that the full stop, comma, and apostrophe are only used once throughout the poem, although dashes are frequently employed.

The poem is determined to be composed of nouns, pronouns, common nouns, verbs, adverbs, and adjectives on a lexical level, with nouns appearing first and adverbs appearing last in terms of frequency.

On the grammatical level, it is discovered that punctuation impacts the poem's structure and aids in conveying the poet's ideas. According to Ali, Bhatti, and Shah (2016), Dickinson employs dashes to demonstrate several literary techniques, including pausing and considering new ideas, pondering what to say next, highlighting obstacles and difficulties she had in life, and altering and interrupting the rhythmic flow. Additionally, they claim that full sentences are employed to convey the poetess' complete thought process and that commas are used to indicate the division of stanzas. According to their phonological analysis, the poem is an ABCD-ABAB-ABBB rhyme verse. The poet frequently employs alliteration in this passage. It can be located on lines three, six, and ten. The poem also makes use of personification, tropes, plans, anaphora, metaphor, and other literary devices. Dickinson describes "Hope" as having the "power to take someone up as birds soar in the sky" and describes it as having feathers or resembling a bird (Ali, Bhatti, and Shah, 2016). They conclude that the poetic variations are a reflection of Dickinson's personal life experiences.

Since both studies analyze poetry and do so using a stylistic approach, they are extremely comparable to the journal article. The difference is the authors and one of the levels of the stylistic approach.

A further study is a term paper titled "Stylistic analysis of Ted Hughes" poem "The Casualty". The analysis is carried out at many stylistic levels, including the graphological, phonological, morphological, and lexico-syntactic levels. Mukhtar discovers the use of capitalization and different types of punctuation to emphasize specific areas at the graphological level. Alliteration, assonance, consonance, and rhyme are used at the phonological level to create aural effects that are attractive to the reader. Affixes are used at the morphological level to modify word meaning. The employment of characters, figurative languages, symbols, imagery, nouns, pronouns, verbs, adverbs, and adjectives at the lexico-syntactic level is necessary to comprehend both the literal and figurative meaning. Ted Hughes is portrayed as a defenseless

guy in this poem by an aviation disaster, in Mukhtar's opinion, makes him a sympathetic figure. When an accident occurs, bystanders are powerless to assist the injured guy.

The similarities between this research and Mukhtar's study are that both of them analyze poetry stylistically. Additionally, there are discrepancies between the article and this research in terms of the number of poems examined, the poems chosen as the study's subject, and its objectives.

A research paper by Muhammad Tahir Anjum titled "Stylistic Analysis of Daud Kamal's Reproduction" (2021). He used linguistic methods like phonological, semantic, structural, grammatical, and some stylistic strategies to analyze the poetry by Daud Kamal for his research work. Additionally, the study uses linguistic tools to investigate the poem's stated meaning. The results of the study indicate that Kamal's use of language results in his writing having visuals and omniscient agony.

The graphological level is concerned with the writing system. According to graphology, the poem is composed of three stanzas, each with seven lines, or a septet. The first letter of the first line is capitalized at the start of each stanza as is customary. Oddly, the remaining lines in each verse start with little letters. According to lexical analysis, the poem has nouns, pronouns, verbs, and adjectives. Assonance, consonance, alliteration, and rhyming parts are just a few of the literary devices that are examined and evaluated at the phonological level. The researcher discovered assonance, consonance, and alliteration in the poem, but no rhyme scheme. The poet's usage of free and bound morphemes as well as affixes is examined at the morphological level, which focuses on word structure. Syntactic concerns itself with sentence form, and parallelism is also a syntactic device. In the first two stanzas, the poet employs a parallel construction, which is examined. On a semantic level, pay attention to how phrases and words are phrased. According to the researcher's analysis, Daud Kamal incorporated historical allusions in his poetry, including Prince Siddhartha, old Tajiks, and sculptures from the Gandhara and Mughal eras.

An explorative study by Muhammad Shakeel ur Rehman and Dr. Faria Saeed Khan named "The Study of Daud Kamal's Poem A Remote Beginning from the Perspective of Stylistics". The researcher analyzes the poetry from the standpoint of stylistic levels, including pragmatics, phonological, and morphological levels, from their research. To reveal hidden meaning and

thematic layers in the chosen poem, the scholars also try to analyze the poem's structure through language features.

The poem is examined at the phonological level, which focuses on the two types of literary devices—sound devices and literary devices—in a literary work. It is determined that the poem has four stanzas of five lines each and a free rhyme scheme, demonstrating the poet's unrestricted use of his imagination and ideas. Consonance, assonance, and alliteration are also explored in the poem. It is discovered that the poet's tone is melancholy and sad at the pragmatic level, which focuses on the context-based meaning of a piece. The poem starts with the line "This Night," in which the night, stands for the ambiguity and unpredictability of the time and place. In the same way that he thinks "This Night" won't last and will soon vanish, it appears that the poet is trying to find some optimism amid his absolute pessimism. The usage of paradox by the poet is also discovered, as is clear from the poem's title, "A Remote Beginning." Normally, an end should be distant or far from the beginning rather than the other way around. Finally, a rhetorical query that the poet employed as the finest instrument to persuade the reader of the subject is examined on a pragmatic level. Affixes and some bound and free morphemes are present at the morphological level.

This section will explore related theories and introduce the ideas that must be used in this study, namely stylistics, phonology, graphology, grammar, and semantics.

B. Related theories;

2.1 Stylistics

Style is a literary discourse that derives from a linguistic alignment. According to Widdowson, the study of literary discourse from a linguistic perspective is known as stylistics (1975). Additionally, stylistics is the study of unique language expression and the explanation of its meaning and results (Verdonk, 2002). So, it may be said that the study of literary discourse in language and its linguistic intent is referred to as stylistics.

In stylistics, a variety of language levels can be seen, especially in poems. To set themselves apart from other poets, a poet develops a unique writing style. The diction, word

choice, punctuation, use of metaphorical language, and other elements all can be used to identify the style. Additionally, style serves as a conduit for the reader to understand a particular message. The style is used for a certain objective. For instance, if a poet wants to convey a hidden meaning in a poem that can change the stated meaning of the entire poem, he or she can do it by utilizing figurative language. When stylistic elements are used in literary works, readers might interpret and respond to the text in specific ways. Both literary and non-literary writings can benefit from the use of stylistics. As a result, language style analysis is always possible.

The four levels of language properties that can be used for stylistic analysis are described by Simpson's language level theory of 2004. These are the semantic level, phonological level, graphological level, and level of grammar. The pronunciation of words in spoken language is known as phonology. The structure of written language is known as graphology. Grammar describes how words are used in conjunction to create phrases and sentences. Semantics is the study of word and sentence meaning.

2.1.1 Phonology

The study of sound systems is called phonology. According to Simpson, phonology includes the meaning that can be attached to spoken language sounds (2004, p. 6). In written text, the way a word is formed determines which sound it makes and how it links to other sounds. Words in the poem form a pattern of sounds that convey meaning. Alliteration, assonance, consonance, and rhymes are all examples of sound patterns that are investigated at the phonological level.

a) Alliteration

Alliteration is the practice of using the same consonant sound at the start of words within a single line of poetry (Hashmi, 2019). Bradford defines alliteration as the recurrence of a group of the same consonant sound both within as well as across line sequences (2005, p. 16). Alliteration happens when the same starting sound recurs in the same line inside the same stanza of the poem, it can be interpreted. Alliteration is a literary device that can be used to highlight specific emotions, reflect the ideas or sensations being portrayed, and improve the aesthetic appeal of writing. In Robert Frost's poem "Birches," the phrase "As the stir cracks and crazes their enamel"

is an example of alliteration. The sound /er/ appears multiple times in that line. The sound of ice breaking and trees rubbing against one another can be compared to the sound of /er/. Frost attempts to convey the sentiments of nature in that both orally and in writing.

b) Assonance

In assonance, the vowel sound is repeated. Assonance, according to Bradford, is the repeating of groups of comparable vowels both within and across sequences of lines (Bradford, *stylistics*, 2005, p.16). When a vowel sound appears more than once in a line of poetry, assonance results. The use of assonance in William Wordsworth's poem "Daffodils".

The vowel sound /o/ is repeated three times in the line:

"A host, of golden daffodils"

c) Consonance

Alliteration and consonance have similarities. The first consonant sound of the alliteration is repeated. Consonance, on the other hand, is recurrence at the beginning and conclusion. Cuddon defines consonance as a near repetition of the same consonant sound after a different vowel (2013, p. 135). "Poem 315" by Emily Dickinson is a poem that uses consonance.

To provide a sense of mood in the poem, the consonant sound /l/ is repeated in the line

"Your brain to bubble cool,
Deals one imperial thunderbolt."

d) Rhyme

Wales claims that rhyme is a specific type of phonetic echo that can be detected in poetry (2011). The repeating of related sounds inside a single stanza is known as rhyme. The rhyme in the poem is purposefully created by the poet to convey a certain point or to add a decorative element. Eye rhyme, masculine rhyme, feminine, slant, para, end, and internal rhyme are a few of the major categories of rhyme.

i. Masculine rhyme

According to Wales (2011), masculine rhyme usually has a monosyllabic content word and is a "strong" rhyme. Since the latter part of the sixteenth century, men's rhyme has been used in the conventional prosody. For example,

Stand the church clock at ten to **three**?

And is there honey still for **tea**?

ii. Feminine rhyme

Multisyllabic, "unstressed endings are a feature of feminine rhymes". (Wales, 2011, p. 156).

E.g. Little Jack Horner

Sat in the **corner**

Slant rhyme

Repetition of the first and last consonants is referred to as slant rhyme, as in **"/bend/"** and **"/band/"**.

iii. Para rhyme

Some people make use of rhyming words when their final consonant sound alike by the terms "para rhyme" or "half-rhyme."

Like **"ill"** and **"shell."**

iv. Internal rhyme

An internal rhyme occurs within a single line of the poem. The opening line of Shelly's The Cloud is used in the example.

E.g. I bring fresh **"/showers/"** for the thirsting **"/flowers/"**

v. End rhyme

The most common rhyme in English is end rhyme. End rhyme, according to Wales, consists of two units that are matched by similar sound sequences that extend from the vowel (typically stressed) to the word's end, with the initial sound altered.

E.g. /rose/ and /toes/

vi. Eye rhyme

Eye rhyme is the rhyme in which the words are spelled the same way but are pronounced differently.

E.g. /bough/ and /cough/

2.1.2 Graphology

According to Gomez, graphology is a level of linguistics analysis that includes the study of linguistic graphics (2015). The study of handwriting patterns and physical traits is called graphology, and it aims to identify the author. Punctuation in language texts is covered by graphology. The reader may be more affected and given more significance by linguistic texts with deliberate graphology. Furthermore, poetry in particular has no restrictions. The author is free to produce a poem by selecting graphology to generate an impression of a specific interpretation.

a) Capitalization

The act of writing or putting words in capital letters is known as capitalization. According to Trask, words that must be written in capital letters are (1) the first word of sentences, (2) the name of days or months, (3) the name of languages, (4) the name of places, (5) nationalities or ethnic groups, (6) proper names, (7) the name of historical periods, (8) the name of holidays, (9) religious terms, (10) the first word and significant words in a title, (11) the first word of direct quotations, (12) brand names, (13) roman numerals, and (14) the pronoun (1997, pp.71-84).

The first letter of each starting word in a line is frequently capitalized in poems. According to Rios (2000), capitalizing the first letter of each starting word in a line of poetry is

regarded as customary and traditional. He goes on to say that this is how poetry is distinguished from other literary works.

b) Punctuation

According to Calhoun, one of the poet's nonverbal weapons for poetic expression is punctuation (Calhoun, 2015). In a linguistic document, punctuation also helps to convey meaning.

1. Period (.)

A period, often known as a full stop, is a punctuation mark used at the end of a sentence to close it.

2. The comma (,)

A comma is used to break up long sentences to make them simpler to read.

3. Apostrophe (’)

An apostrophe is used to signify possession and to indicate the letter omission (Ahmad and Arshad, 2015).

4. Dash (-)

A dash is used to indicate a major break or stoppage in a sentence.

This punctuation is used when two sentences are similar or belong together.

5. Semicolon

This punctuation mark is used when two sentences are similar or go together. A semicolon can be used in between two sentences instead of a comma.

6. Colon

In advance of providing an example or examples of anything, a colon is used.

7. Ellipses

Ellipses is a set of three periods indicating an omission.

8. Hyphen

A hyphen is a type of punctuation mark known as a dash, or minus sign that is used to join words or parts of words.

2.1.3 Grammatical level

The sentence structure is considered at this level. According to Fromkin, "If word sequences forming a sentence is following the rules of grammar, the sentence is grammatical" (200, p. 90). One of the most crucial grammatical components in the English language is tense. The use of the tense describes when a specific action occurs. The tense that will be examined is simple present tense and present continuous tense.

a) Simple Present Tense

According to Yule, the present tense is the most fundamental sentence form. It is linked to the "actual habitual" in the present tense and is demonstrated with an expression of time (1998). In general, the simple present tense is used to communicate facts (universal truth), routine occurrences, and actual happenings. Since the simple present tense refers to events that are currently occurring, it frequently uses time and frequency adverbs like now, today, sometimes, always, occasionally, and so forth. She regularly eats breakfast (habitual), and the sun rises in the east (universal truth), which are examples of simple present tense.

b) Present continuous tense

As the name implies, the present continuous tense is a type of tense used to express an action that is ongoing or occurring at the time. It is also known as the present progressive tense since it represents an action that is happening in the present. The present continuous tense is defined as "a verb form consisting of an auxiliary be in the present tense followed by a present participle and used especially to indicate that a present action or event is in progress, being repeated, or of a temporary nature, or to express the future," according to Collins dictionary.

2.1.3 Semantic level

The meaning of words and sentences is referred to as the semantic level, according to Sampson (2004, p. 5). Wales noted that semantics, in particular, is the study of how words and phrases are interpreted linguistically. Throughout its history, semantics has been greatly impacted by philosophy and logic (2011, p, 379). Wales identifies four different categories of semantics: lexical semantics, phrase semantics, narrative semantics, and literary semantics (2011, p. 380). The most typical kind of semantics is lexical semantics. It is the study of the meaning of individual words, particularly in the context of literary techniques such as metaphor and other literary devices that can transform the meanings of words and phrases. Lexical semantics considers several factors such as context, or the text around a word that gives it a specific meaning, and delicacy, or shades of meaning in a word. The study of sentence semantics focuses on the relationships between terms or roles, such as agent and patient that affect how sentences are understood. When discussing subjects like possible words, narrative semantics is concerned with how often these discussions take place. Some form of philosophy has an impact on narrative semantics. The final category is literary semantics, which is used to support a psychological, philosophical, or general theoretical approach to the dynamics of a literary text. In this study, lexical semantics, which includes figurative language like metaphor, simile, symbols, and imagery, is examined.

a. Metaphor

The word metaphor is derived from the Greek word for "carry-over" (Wales, 2011, p.265). A metaphor is a comparison of two unrelated objects. A direct comparison is a type of metaphor. The poem "The Sun Rising" by John Donne serves as an example of a metaphor.

"She is all states, and all prince, I.

Nothing else is.

Prince do but play us; compared to this,

All honor's mimic, all wealth alchemy."

In the example given above, it can be explained that the man says that his beloved is like every nation on the globe, demonstrating their strong love.

b. Simile

The word simile is derived from the Latin "similes". Wales claims that the figure of speech simile compares two concepts creatively and descriptively (2011, p. 383). Because similes use the words "like" and "as," it is possible to say that they are indirect comparisons. An illustration of a simile can be found in Robert Burns' poem, "A Red, Red Rose":

O my Luve is like a red, red rose

That's newly sprung in June;

O my Luve is like the melody

That's sweetly played in tune.

As can be seen from the verse above, Burns likens his sweetheart to a red rose and melody. A red rose is a literary symbol of both beauty and real love. Burns wants to make it clear that he genuinely adores the beauty of his beloved in this passage. He also compares his sweetheart to melody, which is related to harmony. Burns makes an effort to convey how his lover is a song that makes his life ideal.

c. Symbolism

A symbol, which derives from the Greek word for "token," is a sign that stands in for another idea within a speech community. Different domains may develop their unique collections of symbols. Examples of generic symbols used in literature include the seasons (spring symbolizes life and birth, winter symbolizes death, etc.) and literary "symbols" which are a prominent topic of study in literary criticism (Wales, 2011, p. 408). Ideas are indirectly denoted by symbols; their meaning is not made clear. Our culture may also contain other literary symbols, such as the rose, which stands for love and beauty. However, a symbol can also be an idiolect, which simply implies it was produced by a certain writer. William Blake's symbolism as

W.B. Literature's use of symbolism demonstrates how well we understand how to interpret and

situate literary works. Emily Dickenson's poem "A Light Exist in Spring" serves as an illustration of symbolism in poetry.

A light exists in spring

Not present on the year

At any other period-

When March is scarcely here...

Dickenson uses 'a light' as a symbol of hope and happiness in the poem above.

d. Imagery

Which initially had a visual meaning and is still popular in semiotics when it comes to a physical impersonation of an object like a sculpture, painting, or mosque. it refers to a single shot in a well-edited dramatic sequence (Wales, 2011, p. 215). Both in prose and poetry, literary imagery serves a purpose beyond mere decoration. For instance, to support characters, places, or themes. The poem "My November Guest" by Robert Frost serves as an illustration of imagery.

"My sorrow when she is here with me,

Thinks these **dark** days of autumn rain

Are beautiful as days can be;

She loves the bare, the withered tree;

She walked the sodden posture lane."

Frost utilizes the term "black" as imagery in the poem above, which stands for the undesirable or worst autumn rain days. The term "black" is not just used for aesthetic purposes; it also serves to emphasize how terrible the situation is in the poem "My November Guest".

CHAPTER 3

Methodology

There are three parts to this chapter. They serve as the study's subject, framework, and methodology. Poems serve as the study's subject, and language aspects are used to examine them. The study's strategy reveals the kind of methodology used in the current study to examine the linguistic features. The study's methodology explains the data collection and analysis procedures used by the author.

3.1 Object of the study

The two poems by Daud Kamal—"A *Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*"—that will be the subject of the study are taken from one of his posthumous books, "A Collection of Verse," which was published in 1997 by Oxford University Press. There are 49 poems by Daud Kamal in the book. The poems under discussion are constructed in various ways. Each of the four stanzas of the first poem, "*A shadow is Not a Memory*," includes six lines, except for the final stanza, which has only two. The second poem, "*Erasure*", has three stanzas with six lines each.

Based on their language levels, including phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic levels, the study assessed the aforementioned poems from a stylistic standpoint.

3.2 Approach of the Study

In this study, the stylistic approach was used since it is the best method for analyzing literary works. The two poems by Daud Kamal that were analyzed in the study are "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". The study of how meaning is expressed through language in literature and other types of text is known as stylistics (Norgard, Montoro, & Busse, 2010, p.1.). By discussing the language elements in the poem, the poem's meaning can be revealed. According to Leech and Short, the study of style in linguistics is known as stylistics. (1981, p.13). Because the current study examines linguistic aspects in literary works, specifically in the poems "*A Shadow*

is Not a Memory" and *"Erasure"* by Daud Kamal, it is appropriate to employ stylistics as the study's approach.

In the current study, the stylistic method served as the guiding concept for analyzing the literary text, which is poetry. The poems feature linguistic components such as phonology, graphology, grammar, and semantics. The linguistic components at each language level would be exposed in stylistics. The researcher shows how linguistic features are used to reveal the meaning of the poem after figuring out their existence.

3.3 Method of the Study

Two sections make up the study's methodology. The gathering of data comes first, and its analysis comes second. The data collection describes in what way the data are gathered, whereas the analysis of data describes how the data are examined.

3.3.1 Data Collection

The study made use of a data population method, "which is typical when data share a single attribute" (Best & Kahn, 2014, p. 11). The poems *"Erasure"* and *"A Shadow is Not a Memory"* by Daud Kamal are used as the study's sources of data for the language features they include. The author of both poems, Daud Kamal, is a common characteristic shared by both poems. Literature texts that were picked from the entirety of the poems served as the study's population. The study's data collection process included several steps.

Choosing the type of literary work to be evaluated was the first stage. The selection of poems is based on their brevity. Due to the short amount of time available for investigation, the researcher decided to focus on a poem. Also, because poems are little in length, it is possible to read the entire text.

The selection of the poet and the poems from that poet to be employed in the research came next. Daud Kamal is one of the most talented poets in Pakistan, therefore his poems were chosen. He was a mystic poet, and his poems included important subjects like spirituality, mysticism, and pastoral and country life, among others.

The researcher then chose which poems of Daud Kamal should be examined. The selection of the poetry to be evaluated can be aided by a few parameters. The researcher's top priority when selecting the poems was that they not have been previously used in stylistic studies. The researcher chose the poems "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*" from the poetry book "*A Selection of Verse*" by Daud Kamal, which is available in soft form on the website Scribd.com, because of their distinctive styles and shared topics.

3.3.2 Data Analysis

In the sections that follow, numerous steps were completed in an effort to respond to two research questions that were formulated. To address the two study issues, the poems were examined at four different linguistic levels, including phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic.

The language aspects in the data were first examined by the researcher by developing four tiers. Alliteration, consonance, assonance, and rhyme scheme were all examined by the researcher at the phonological level in the poems.

The researcher focused on the repeat of the first consonant sound in each line when studying alliteration. Contrary to alliteration which is the repetition of the first consonant, consonance is characterized by the repeating of a middle or final consonant. The repetition of a vowel is known as assonance. The researcher focused on various types of rhyming schemes.

Following the observation of the graphological level, the researcher concentrated on capitalization and punctuation, such as commas, dashes, and question marks. In the poems, capitalization is also noticeable.

The poems were then examined based on their grammatical complexity. By examining the tenses employed in the poem as well as the sentence structure, it was possible to determine the poem's grammatical level. The tenses indicated various timelines that might provide a specific interpretation of the poem's meaning. The final level is semantic; the researcher identified a number of rhetorical devices in the poem that helped to establish its meaning.

Second, following the study of the linguistic elements in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". By relating the sentences and other language elements employed in the poems, the researcher deduced the significance of each poem. Additionally, to be able to respond to the second phrasing of the problem. To determine the meaning of the poems of Daud Kamal, the researcher examined their linguistic characteristics. After analyzing the language elements, the poems' meaning was discovered.

3.4 Theoretical Framework

Several theories have previously been examined as the theories that will help the researcher come up with solutions to the issues. The current study takes a stylistics-based method, therefore Paul Simpson's language level theory is applied in the present study to help the researcher identify the language aspects in the poems "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". To do stylistic analysis, according to Simpson, is to examine language, and more specifically, to explore creativity in language use. Simpson presents the levels of language through which a piece of text or utterance is arranged, which can help organize and define a stylistic analysis. These levels are phonological, graphological, morphological, grammatical, semantic, and pragmatic level. The meaning of the poems would be continuously revealed through the usage of linguistic elements.

Language properties will be examined on four different levels: phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantics. At the phonological level, the researcher applies phonological theories to identify rhyme, assonance, consonance, and alliteration patterns in the poem. Punctuation is covered by the theories at the graphological level. The tenses in the poem serve as the theories' data on the grammatical level; that is basic present tense. On the semantic level, the researcher employs figurative devices found in the poem, such as metaphor, simile, imagery, and symbolism to help the author clarify the meaning of the poems "*A Shadow is not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*" to address the second problem, which is to reveal the meaning of the poems.

CHAPTER 4

Data Analysis

This section offers a discussion and analysis of the problem formulation. The language qualities that can be seen in both of Kamal's poems are identified in the first phase of the analysis, and they are then broken down. The first section is continued in the second section. The language features that have been broken down help to clarify the interpretation of each poem.

Language features in Daud Kamal's "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*"

The first research question is addressed in this section of the analysis by examining the linguistic features of Daud Kamal's "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*" poems. The Simpson theory, which was discussed in the previous chapter, is used to analyze language features. The features are examined at the phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic levels.

4.1 Language features in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*"

The first literary piece examined in the study is "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*." Using Simpson's theory as a foundation, the language elements of the poem are examined at the phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic levels.

4.1.1 Phonological level

A poem is made up of words that have been purposefully organized to maintain continuity from one word to the next. The study of stylistic elements in a poem can be determined via the phonological level. Phonology is the study of sound systems, as was previously said. Segmental and Suprasegmental sound elements are the two types of sound systems that exist at the phonological level. Alliteration, consonance, and assonance are examples of segmental sound features. Rhyme and meter are examples of Suprasegmental sound features. Only the rhyme is examined in the current study.

A. Segmental Sound Feature

Alliteration, consonance, and assonance are the elements the researcher discovers in Daud Kamal's poem "A Shadow is Not a Memory". As a result, certain sound qualities are examined, which aids the researcher in determining the author's intentions. The following is a presentation of the analysis.

a) Alliteration

In the poem, first of all, the researcher analyzes alliteration. Alliteration is the art of starting each word in a line of poetry with the same consonant sound (Mahmood, 2019). Alliteration is the reoccurrence of a group of comparable consonant sounds inside individual lines and throughout sequences of lines, according to Bradford (2005, p. 16). They are termed clusters because each sound in a cluster can be heard. To sum up, alliteration happens when the same starting sound appears more than once in a poem's same line or stanza. Here are examples of repetitions from the poem.

Table 1. Alliteration in the poem "A Shadow is Not a Memory"

No	Alliteration	Example
1	/s/	Suddenly years are swallowed up
2	/ð/	That is no longer there.

In the poem "A Shadow is Not a Memory" the researcher discovered two instances of alliteration. The consonants that undergo alliteration are /s/, and /ð/.

In stanza 1, there are no alliteration. In stanza 2, there is only one alliteration found. The consonant that is repeated is an alveolar voiceless fricative /s/, shown below;

Suddenly years are swallowed up (line 3, stanza 2)

In stanza 3, there is also only one alliteration occurs that are spotted in line 6 of the respective stanza. The recurrent consonant is dental voiced fricative /ð/, as shown below;

That is no longer **th**ere (line 6, stanza 3)

There are no alliteration found in the 4th and the last stanza which consist of two lines.

b) Assonance

Assonance is another type of sound that can be heard in the poem. Bradford defines assonance as the repeating of a cluster of similar vowels within a single line and via line sequences (Stylistics, 2005, p.16). In short, assonance is the recurrence of a vowel inside a singleline of poetry. The following is a list of the assonance in the poem;

Table 2. Assonance in the poem “A Shadow is Not a Memory”

No	Assonance	Frequency	Example
1	/ɪ/	6	Refracting your image (line 5, stanza 1)
2	/ə/	5	A shadow is not a memory (line 2, stanza 4)
3	/ʌ/	2	Suddenly years are swallowed up (line 3, stanza2)

In the poem “A Shadow is Not a Memory”, there are 3 occurrences of assonance, with /ɪ/, /ə/, and /ʌ/ as the repeated sound. In the poem, assonance /ɪ/ is the dominating one. The phonetic features of /ɪ/ are front high. It occurs 6 times in the poem. The words “refracting”, and “image” in line 5 of the first stanza are examples. The next assonance is the sound /ə/, which occurs 5 times in the poem. Its phonetic features are central mid-unrounded. One of the examples is the second line of stanza 4. The examples can be seen in the words “a”, “shadow”, “a”, and “memory”. The third assonance found in the poem is /ʌ/, 2 times happens. Its phonetic features are central mid vowels. The example can be seen in the words “suddenly”, and “up” in the third line of the second stanza.

b) Consonance

The final segmental characteristic examined in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” is consonance. Cuddon defines consonance as the adjoining recurrence of the same consonant sound after various vowels (2013, p. 153). Consonance, in contrast to alliteration, also appears in the middle and at the end of the sentence. The following are the consonances from the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”.

Table 3. Consonance in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

No	Consonance	Frequency	Example
1	/r/	12	R efracting your image (line5, stanza1)
2	/n/	4	U nder a n a ncient bridge (line2, stanza1)
3	/l/	2	It l eans upon a w all (line4, stanza3)
4	/z/	2	It broods over faces (line3, stanza3)
5	/m/	1	There are flame- m irrors (line1, stanza2)
6	/d/	1	S uddenly years are swallowed u p (line3, stanza2)
7	/w/	1	A w irl of w ater (line1, stanza1)
8	/k/	1	It cannot r ecalls (line4, stanza3)

In the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”, there are 8 consonances that occur. Consonance /r/ occurs the most, it happens 12 times. Alveolar voiceless fricative is the phonetic feature of /r/. The example is in line 5, stanza 1, as shown below;

Refracting your image (line 5, stanza1)

The second consonance spotted in the poem is /n/ that occurs four times in the poem. Alveolar nasal-voiced are the phonetic features of /n/. Example of the consonance /n/ can be seen in the second line of the first stanza in the words “under”, “an”, and “ancient”. The third consonance found in the poem is /l/, which occurs two times in the poem. Alveolar later liquid (voiced) is the phonetic feature of consonance /l/. An example of the consonance /l/ can be seen in the fourth line of the third stanza in the words “leans”, and “wall”. The fourth consonance observed in the poem is /z/ that occurs two times in the poem. Alveolar voiced fricatives are the phonetic features of the consonance /z/. The example of consonance /z/ that is demonstrated in line 3 of stanza 3 in the words “broods”, and “faces”.

The fifth consonance found in the poem is /m/ occurs 1 time in the poem in line 1 of stanza 2 demonstrated in the words “flame” and “mirrors”. Bilabial nasal-voiced are the phonetic features of the consonance /m/. The sixth consonance spotted in the poem is /d/ in line 3 of stanza 2 which can be observed in the words “suddenly”, and “swallowed”. Alveolar voiced stop (oral) are the phonetic features of consonance /d/. The seventh consonance found in the poem is /w/ just a single time in the poem in the first line of the first stanza in the words “swirl”, and “water”. Voiced bilabial glide is the phonetic feature of consonance /w/. The eighth consonance found in the poem is /k/ that also spotted one time in the poem in line 4 of stanza 3 in the words “cannot”, and “recall”. Velar voiceless stop are the phonetic features of consonance /k/.

According to the analysis, Kamal uses the three segmental features in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”. Consonance is the sound feature that is used most frequently, as there are 8 different consonants that are repeated throughout the poem. Assonance is preceded by consonance with 3 occurrences and alliteration with 2 occurrences.

B. Supersegmental sound features

The final sound component, rhyme, is examined in this section. The nucleus and coda at the end of lines are repeated to create a rhyme. (Ufot, 2013, p. 118). The poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” is made up of four stanzas, with six lines in three stanzas and two lines in the fourth stanza. The rhyme of the poem is clear from the way it is structured. In the poem, there are three rhymes found.

Table 4. Rhymes in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

No	Type of Rhymes	Example	Rhyme
1	Para-rhyme	Under an ancient bridge (line 2, stanza 1) Refracting your image (line 5, stanza 1)	ɪdʒ
2	Para-rhyme	There are flame- mirrors (line 1, stanza 2) I dream of swelling rivers (line 5, stanza 2)	əz
3	Para-rhyme	It cannot recall (line 4, stanza 3) It leans upon a wall (line 5, stanza 3)	ɔːl

4.1.2 Graphological level

This level examines the poem's graphological features “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”, focusing on spellings, use of ellipses, contractions, hyphens, quotation marks, colon, semicolon, period, full stop, use of capitalizations, gothic or bold letters, etc. the first part of the analyzes capitalization in the poem while punctuation in the poem is covered in the second section.

a) Capitalization

Capitalization is the first graphological characteristic. Every word's first letter in every line is written in capital letters, which is customary and frequent in poetry. (Rios, 2000). The poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” consist of 4 stanzas, three stanzas consist of six lines each while the last one consists of two lines.

In the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” Daud Kamal didn’t follow any set rule or pattern for capitalization. In the first stanza, the poet used to capitalize the first letter of the first line while skipping to capitalize the first letter of the next two lines. Besides, the fourth line of the respective stanza starts with a capital letter and then skips capitalization in the next two lines.

The second stanza starts with a capital letter while skipping the capitalization in the second line, again the third line starts with the capital letter then skip to capitalize the first letter of the fourth line. Furthermore, the fifth line starts with the capital letter while avoiding capitalization in the sixth one.

In the third stanza, the poet capitalizes the first letter of the first line of the stanza and the first letter of the third one and avoids capitalizing the remaining lines. In the last stanza, the fourth one, the poet capitalizes the first letter of both lines of the stanza. In conclusion, it is found that the poem has a disturbed pattern of capitalization which shows the disturbance in the life of the poet.

b) Punctuation

Punctuation is the next graphological feature found in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”. In the poem there are four punctuation marks spotted in the poem that is ellipses, commas, dash, and full stops, as shown below;

Table 5. Punctuation found in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

No	Punctuation	Frequency	Example
1	Full stop (.)	7	The air smells of rock. (line 1, stanza4)
2	Ellipses (...)	3	Under an ancient bridge... (line 2, stanza 1)
3	Coma (,)	1	Refracting your image, (line 4, stanza1)

4	Hyphen (-)	1	There are flame-mirrors (line 1, stanza 2)
5	Dash (—)	1	It cannot recall__ (line 4, stanza 3)

1. Full stop or Period

When the idea of a sentence is complete, a full stop or period is used. In the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”, Daud Kamal punctuates his sentences with a period 7 times in line 6 of the first stanza, lines 2, 4, and 6 of the second stanza, lines 2 and 6 of the third stanza, and at the end of both two lines of the fourth stanza.

2. Ellipses

The first punctuation spotted in the poem is ellipses. Ellipses are a set of three dots or periods that indicate the omission. Each period should have space on either side, except when adjacent to a quotation mark. Ellipses occur three times in the poem in just the first stanza, at the end of lines 2, 3, and 4 respectively shown below;

Under an ancient bridge. . .

Plumage of stars. . .

The bubbles come and go...

3. Coma

The second punctuation found in the poem is coma with just one occurrence in the poem, at the end of the fourth line of the first stanza that indicates a brief pause before the poet begins the next line, as shown below;

Refracting your image,

4. Dash

A dash denotes separation stronger than a comma, less formally than a colon, and more casually than a parenthesis (Strunk William, 1999, p. 20). The purpose of dashes is to separate groups of words. En (-) dash and em (___) dash are the two types of dashes used in the poem. Daud Kamal uses em dash to show emphasis and silence before the next sentence in the thirdline of the third stanza that is;

It cannot recall___

4.1.4 Grammatical level

At this stage, the research tends to focus on the tenses employed in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”. According to Yule, “tenses serve to locate situation in time” (Yule, 1998, p. 54). There are two types of tenses used in the poem by Daud Kamal as shown below;

Table 6. Tenses in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

No	Tense	Frequency	Example
1	Simple present tense	18	I dream of swelling rivers (line 5, stanza 2)
2	Present continuous tense	2	Refracting your image (line 5, stanza 1)

At this level, the focus of the researcher is on the tense that is used in the poem. The two types of tenses mentioned above are used by Daud Kamal. The present simple tense is used for the sentence structure in the line below;

I dream of swelling rivers (line 5, stanza 2)

Firstly, in this line, the subject is “I”, the verb is “dream”, and the object is “swelling rivers”, while “of” work as a subject genitive. The sentence has the simple present tense structure of sub+v1+obj. The present simple tense denotes "a current state: a sensation, opinion, orrelation. The fact that Daud Kamal employs the simple present tense is evidence of his feeling in the present scenario about life. He accepts the fact that life will go on with the hardships and those will become a memory that would be like a shadow that exists for a time being.

Refracting your image (line 5, stanza 1)

In the sentence above “refracting” acts as the verb. “Your image” acts as the object. This line uses the form of present continuous/progressive tense, which is sub+be+v1+ing+obj. The verb here in this line is **refracting**, the first form of the verb and ing “**refract+ing**”, therefore, line 5 of the first stanza uses progressive tense to show the continuity of the action in the present time.

It is safe to assume based on the study above that Daud Kamal primarily utilizes the simple present tense. The present tense is used to describe things that are happening right now, broad truths, and facts. In “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”, Daud Kamal uses simple present and present continuous tense to let the reader feel as though they are reading the poetry; this will help the readers better interpret and comprehend the poem.

4.1.4 Semantic level

The semantic features in “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” is analyzed at this level. The poem uses the figure of speech to present semantic elements including symbol, imagery, metaphor, and personification as shown below;

Table 7. Figurative language in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

No	Rhetorical devices	Example
1	Symbolism	Under an ancient bridge___ (line 2, stanza 1)

		<p>There are flame-mirrors</p> <p>In every thornbush.</p> <p>(line 1,2, stanza 2)</p> <p>I dream of swelling rivers</p> <p>And thundering horses</p> <p>(line 5,6 stanza 2)</p> <p>The air smells of rock.</p> <p>(line 1, stanza 4)</p>
2	Imagery	<p>A swirl of water</p> <p>(line 1, stanza 1)</p> <p>The bubbles come and go...</p> <p>(line 4, stanza1)</p> <p>I dream of swelling river,</p> <p>(line 5, stanza 2)</p>
3	Metaphor	<p>It leans upon a wall</p> <p>(line 5, stanza 3)</p>
4	Personification	<p>Suddenly years are swallowed up</p> <p>By the evening mist</p>

		(line 3,4, stanza 2)
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The first figurative language is symbolism found in the poem. Daud Kamal uses “ancient bridge” in the second line of the first stanza which symbolizes the old version or past of the poet. In line 1, 2 of the second stanza the poet uses the words “flame-mirrors” and “thornbush”. “flame-mirrors” symbolizes desires or hope and “thornbush” symbolizes the hardships of life, so these words symbolize our desire and hope for a good time in the hardships of life. From the words “swelling rivers” and “thundering horses” the poet symbolizes the urge for freedom without restraint like a storm. In the line 1 of last stanza the “rock” symbolizes the obstacles in life and the “air” symbolizes life, so here the poet wants to tell about the obstacles and hurdle that the life he lived seems to him is all about hurdle.

The second figurative device spotted in the poem is imagery. It occurs in the first stanza and the second stanza of the poem. In the first stanza, there is the imagery of an old bridge under which there is a stream flowing with a starry sky, etc. Here this imagery is related to the memories of the poet and the „plumage of stars” represent the night which symbolizes emptiness and coldness, and it also symbolizes the new coming; the switching of darkness to light. The next imagery is “swelling rivers” that is related to the urge of freedom.

The next figurative language used in the poem is metaphor. A metaphor is the comparison of two things having some similarities without using the terms “as” and “like”. In line 5 of stanza 3 leaning upon a wall shows the hope of something from somewhere or someone. The last figurative language personification that is used in the poem. Personification is the attributing of human characteristics to inanimate objects (Cuddon, 2013, p. 529). The lines 3 and 4 show the personification Daud Kamal uses in the poem as shown below;

Suddenly years are swallowed up

By the evening mist

Here the “evening mist” is an inanimate object and the process of swallowing is something that is done by the animate object so this shows the personification of the “evening mist”

4.2 Language Features in “Erasure” poem

The second literary piece discussed in the study is “Erasure”. Similar to the first poem, this one is likewise included in the book “A Collection of Verse” by Daud Kamal. In the book, it is the 28th poem. “Erasure” is made up of three stanzas with 18 lines, one stanza short from the previous poem which makes it a little different.

4.2.1 Phonological level

The phonological features found in the poem “Erasure” is quite similar to “A Shadow is Not a Memory”, the poem discussed before. The features are divided into two; segmental sound features and Supersegmental sound features. The phonetic elements in the poem "Erasure" are remarkably similar to those in the poem that was previously discussed. Segmental sound features and Supersegmental sound features are the two categories into which the features are split. Segmental sound features include alliteration, assonance, and consonance, whereas Supersegmental sound features include rhyme.

A. Segmental Sound Features

Alliteration, assonance, and consonance are the three sound elements that appear in this poem, which are relatively similar to those in the preceding poem.

a) Alliteration

Alliteration is the first sound element at this level. The recurrence of a consonant sound at the start of a word is known as alliteration. In the poem, there are a total of three uses of alliteration.

Table 8. Alliteration found in the poem “Erasure”

No	Alliteration	Example
1	/s/	Straddling sinuous waterfalls (line 3, stanza 2)

2	/w/	With what we like to believe? (line 6, stanza 2)
3	/t/	I try to salvage (line 5, stanza 3)

Those are the alliteration found in the poem “*Erasure*”. Alliteration occurs between the consonants which are /s/, /w/, and /t/.

In stanza 1, there is no alliteration spotted. The first alliteration found in the poem is /s/ in the third line of the second stanza. Alveolar voiceless fricative is the phonetic feature of alliteration /s/. The words that show an example of alliteration /s/ are “straddling” and “sinuous” in the third line of the second stanza. The second alliteration found in the poem also occurs in the second stanza of the poem which is /w/. Bilabial/velar voiced glide are the phonetic features of alliteration /w/. The example can be seen in the words “with”, “what”, and “we” in stanza 2, line 6.

The third alliteration found in the poem occurs in the third stanza of the poem which is /t/. Alveolar voiceless stop are the phonetic features for the alliteration /t/. The alliteration /t/ can be seen through the words “try” and “to” in line 5 of stanza three.

b) Assonance

Beside alliterations, assonance, which is the recurrence of similar vowel sounds, has been found by the researcher in the poem “*Erasure*”. Diphthong is also comprised of assonance as it consists of two vowel sounds. Assonance occurs 7 times in the poem, which is shown below;

Table 9. Assonance found in the poem “*Erasure*”

No	Assonance	Frequency	Example
1	/i/	6	Drift swelling into a tide (line 3, stanza 1)

2	/ɔ/	3	Of that other life (line 2, stanza 2)
3	/æ/	1	As much as it reveals (line 6, stanza 1)
4	/i/	1	With what we like to believe (line 3, stanza 2)
5	/oʊ/	1	Grow old like us. Bleary eyed. (line 2, stanza 3)
6	/aɪ/	1	Grow old like us. Bleary eyed (line 2, stanza3)

There are seven assonances spotted in the poem of which three are diphthongs, those are /i/, /ɔ/, /æ/, /i/, /oʊ/, /aɪ/, and /aɪ/. The most dominant assonance found in the poem is /i/ that occurs 6 times in the poem. Front high is the phonetic features for the assonance /i/. An example of this assonance can be seen in the words “drift”, “swelling”, and “into”. The second assonance found in the poem is /ɔ/ occurs 3 times in the poem. Central mid is the phonetic feature of assonance /ɔ/. Example of the assonance /ɔ/ can be seen through the words “of” and “other”.

The third assonance spotted in the poem is /æ/ occurs just one time in the poem in line 2 of the second stanza. Front low is the phonetic features of assonance /æ/. Examples of assonance /æ/ can be found in the following words “as” and “as” in line 2 of stanza 2. The fourth assonance found in the poem is /i/, which occurs just one time in the poem and can be seen in line 6 of stanza 2 in the words „we“ and “believe”. Front high is the phonetic features of assonance /i/. The fifth assonance found in the poem is /oʊ/occurs one time in the poem in line 2 of stanza 3 in the words “grow” and “old”. The sixth assonance found in the poem is /aɪ/ also occurs just once in the poem in line 2 of stanza 3 in the words “like” and “eyed”. The last assonance found in the poem is /aɪ/ in line 5 of stanza 3 in the words “I” and “try”.

c) Consonance

Consonance, or the repeating of consonantal sounds in any place (Noragaard, Montoro, & Busse, 2010, p. 63), is the final segmental sound element present in the poem. 7 instances of consonance are found in the poem as shown below;

Table 10. Consonance in the poem “Erasure”

No	Consonance	Frequency	Example
1	/l/	6	Straddling sinuous waterfalls (line 3, stanza 2)
2	/t/	4	Petals of nostalgia (line 4, stanza 3)
3	/r/	3	Grow old like us. Bleary eyed, (line 2, stanza 3)
4	/z/	2	As much as it reveals. (line 6, stanza 1)
5	/d/	1	Drift swelling into a tide__ (line 3, stanza 1)
6	/s/	1	Sub-aqueous glow (line 4, stanza 1)
7	/ð/	1	Of that other life__ (line 2, stanza 2)

The most occurred consonance in the poem “Erasure” is /l/ which occurs 6 times. The example can be seen in the words “straddling” and “waterfalls” in line 3 of stanza 2. Alveolar later liquid (voiced) is the phonetic feature of consonance /l/. The second most occurred consonance found in the poem is /t/. It occurs 4 times in the poem. An example of the consonance /t/ can be seen through the words “petals” and “nostalgia” in line 4 of stanza 3.

Alveolar voiceless stop (oral) is the phonetic feature of consonance /t/ are alveolar voiceless stop (oral).

The third assonance found in the poem is /r/ with three occurrences in the poem. Through the words “grow” and “bleary” in line 2 of stanza 3 the example can be observed. Alveolar voiceless fricative is the phonetic feature of consonance /r/. The fourth assonance spotted in the poem is /z/. It occurs two times in the poem. The example is in the words “as”, “as” and “reveals” in the sixth line of the first stanza. Alveolar voiced fricative are the phonetic features of consonance /z/. The fifth assonance found in the poem is /d/occurs one time in the poem.Examples can be seen in the words “drift” and “tide”. Alveolar voiced stop (oral) are the phonetic features of consonance /d/. The sixth assonance spotted in the poem is /s/, which occurs just one time in the poem. An example can be through the words “sub” and “aqueous”. Alveolar voiceless fricative is the phonetic feature of consonance /s/. The last consonance found in the poem is /ð/. It occurs one time in the poem. The words “that” and “other” in line 2 of stanza 3 present the example. Dental voiced fricative are the phonetic features of consonance /ð/.

B. Supersegmental sound features

Similar to the preceding poem, the rhyming in Supersegmental sound properties is examined. The two components that makeup rhyme are the nucleus and the coda (Crystal, 2008, p. 417).

The poem “*Erasure*” by Daud Kamal is a poem of 3 stanzas that includes 18 lines. This poem is a free-versed poem having no rhyme scheme in the entire poem.

4.2.2 Graphological level

The graphical features found in the poem are analyzed at the graphological level. McIntosh (1961) finds graphology similar to phonology. He takes graphology “in a sense which is intended to answer, in the realm of written language, to that of „phonology“ in the realm of spoken language” (pp.107). The first part of the graphological level analyzes the capitalization and the second part analyzes the punctuation used in the poem.

a) Capitalization

The first graphological feature that is analyzed in the poem is capitalization. The poem “*Erasure*” consists of 3 stanzas each consisting of six lines. In the poem, the poet Daud Kamal didn’t follow any set pattern or rule for capitalization. In the first line of the very first stanza which consists of just one word, the poet capitalizes the first letter of the word while skipping to capitalize the remaining 5 five lines of the first stanza.

The second stanza starts with the capital letter “I” personal pronoun then skip the capitalization in the next two lines and capitalize the first letter of the fourth and fifth line respectively and didn’t capitalize the last line of the stanza. The first line of the last stanza which consists of one word starts with a capital letter and then avoids capitalizing the first letter of the second line. Again the next three lines of the last stanza start with the capital letters and skip to capitalize the last line of the stanza.

b) Punctuation

The punctuation marks found in this poem are dash, full stop/period, and question mark, fewer than in the previous poem which has ellipses, full stop/period, and comma, dash, and hyphen. The punctuation marks found in the poem are shown below;

Table 11. Punctuation found in the poem “*Erasure*”

No	Punctuation	Frequency	Example
1	Full stop	7	As much as it reveals. (line 6, stanza 1)
2	Dash	4	Is the premonition of loss____ (line 2, stanza 1)
3	Question mark	1	With what we like to believe? (Line 6. Stanza 2)

The mostly occur punctuation in the poem is the full stop. A full stop indicates the completion of the thoughts of the poet. In the poem “*Erasure*”, Daud Kamal uses a full stop at the end of sentences 7 times. Another punctuation found in the poem is a dash (em dash) that

occurs 4 times in the poem, the second-most frequently used punctuation in Daud Kamal's poem "Erasure". It appears after lines 2 and 3 of the first stanza and 2 and 3 of the second stanza. Dashes at the end of the line show the abrupt change of thoughts of the poet. The last punctuation spotted in the poem is the question mark. It occurs only one time in the poem. The question mark shows the unclear thought of the poet and also acts as a rhetorical device as in line 6 of stanza 2;

Is love clouded

With what we like to believe?

4.2.3 Grammatical level

At the grammatical level, the researcher concentrates on the tenses utilized in the poem "Erasure". Daud Kamal uses simple present tense and present continuous tense in the poem as shown below;

Table 12. Tenses in the poem "Erasure"

No	Tenses	Frequency	Example
1	Simple present tense	12	I try to salvage (line 5, stanza 3)
2	Present continuous tense	4	Is the premonition of loss___ (line 2, stanza 1)

For a present state, such as a mood, opinion, or relationship, the simple present tense is used. (Eastwood, 1994, p. 83). The usage of the verb in its basic form identifies the tense. Simple present tense in general expresses facts, habitual events, and events that exist. The poet Daud Kamal mostly uses simple present tense in the poem, examples are shown below;

I try to salvage (line 5, stanza 3)

In the line above, the subject is “I”, the verb is “try”, “to” is the preposition, and the object is “salvage”. Therefore, this statement uses the sub+v1+obj form of the simple present tense. To convey to the reader that the poem "*Erasure*" is appropriate at any moment, anywhere on anyone, poet Daud Kamal uses the simple present tense. It can be inferred that the poet wishes to provide readers with a timeless description of the poem "*Erasure*." In the poem Daud Kamal also uses present continuous tense to show that the phenomenon of aging, desires, and feeling of losing something happens continuously through the lifetime.

4.2.4 Semantic level

The researcher examines the poetic devices used in "*Erasure*" at the semantic level. According to Simpson, the meaning of words and sentences is semantics. (2004, p. 5). The figurative language used in the poem "*Erasure*" is illustrated below;

Table 13. Figurative devices in the poem “*Erasure*”

No	Type of rhetorical devices	Example
1	Imagery	Drift swelling into a tide___ (line 3, stanza 1) Straddling sinuous waterfalls___ (line 3, stanza 2) The flesh sags. Wrinkles appear. (line 3, stanza 3)
2	Symbolism	Touch (line 1, stanza 1) Mirrors (line 1, stanza 3)
3	Metaphor	Petals of nostalgia. (line 4, stanza 3)
4	Simile	Mirrors grow old like us. Bleary-eyed

The first figurative language is imagery. The poet Daud Kamal uses the imagery of the swelling of drift into a tide. The word drift suggests the gradual movement of something but “swelling into a tide” implies the more forceful and overwhelming sensation of the loss. The next imagery portrays in the poem by the pot is the imagery of waterfalls indicating the meaning of something beyond the reach, risk-taking, and adventure. The third imagery found in the poem is the phenomenon of getting old of humans, which is the sagging of the flesh of humans and appearing wrinkles on the skin, which means getting hold of a person along with his wishes and desires.

The second figurative device found in the poem is symbolism. The word “touch” and “mirrors” are symbolized in the poem by Daud Kamal. Touch symbolizes life and time, and mirrors symbolize the desires and wishes of a person. The third figurative device discovered in the poem is a metaphor. The metaphor compares two things directly without connecting words. The word used as a metaphor by Daud Kamal in the poem “*Erasure*” is “petals” in line 4 of stanza 3. Here, in this line, “petals” refers to the incident of life memories. The last figurative device found in the poem is the simile. In contrast to metaphor, the simile is an indirect comparison of two things. As a result, similes use “as” or “like”. In the second line of stanza 3, the poet uses “like” to compare mirrors with human features that they are old just like human beings get old.

B. The revealed interpretations in “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” and “*Erasure*”

These poems were written by Daud Kamal using phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic language aspects. Due to the significance they convey, these linguistic elements have been carefully chosen. The meanings are represented by looking at the linguistic elements from the four language levels covered in the previous chapter. The following section goes into greater detail on how the language aspects contribute to comprehending the poem's meaning.

4.3 Depression and Hope in “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”

The philosophical principle of “know thy self” was adopted by Daud Kamal, which encourages his readers to understand themselves in order to understand the nature around them.

The poem "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" showcases the depression and sense of loss of the poet and the hope for a good and better time. So the poem is a kind of self-curing in which the poet at first was deeply in depression, in sadness, remembering what he was like in the past and what he is now, and he himself gives courage and hope to himself that these hardships, the time will change soon into better. In conclusion, the poet wanted to give the message of hope and courage in times of depression, and darkness in life after the night the new and bright day will be coming. Below is an explanation of several stylistic elements that are employed to convey the poem's message.

Alliteration, assonance, and consonance play a significant part in phonological segmental elements in illustrating the poem's meaning. Daud Kamal used them to highlight particular words that were important to the poem's message. Line 3 of stanza 2 is an illustration of alliteration;

Suddenly years are swallowed up

In the line above, alliteration occurs in the words "suddenly" and "swallowed". It means that the poet wants to emphasize these words, in this line the poet Daud Kamal wants to tell the sudden changes in life and the swift passing of time that time and life takes unexpected twists that in no time. Another segmental feature is assonance, in the last stanza of the poem as shown below;

The air smells of rock.

A shadow is not a memory.

These two lines above have the entire meaning of the poem. Here in the first line, the poet tells about the hurdles, and the obstacles in life, and then in the very next line he says that whatever bad and sad incidents happen in life with the passage of time it becomes faded and present at one time and at the next moment it disappears like a shadow, faded and not present at all time. The last is consonance, the most occurring segmental feature in the poem, as it occurs inline (5, stanza 1) below;

Refracting your image

The alveolar voiceless fricative /r/ is the consonance that happens mostly in the poem. The word “refracting” implies the distortion of the image of the poet in the water, which is related to his memories, and the friction of the thoughts of the poet almost all over the poem.

In Suprasegmental features, there is rhyme. In the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” only one sort of rhyming occurs, and that is para-rhyme. The rhymed words “bridge” and “image”, “mirrors” and “rivers”, and “recall” and “wall” happens with irregularity. The example is shown below;

Under an ancient bridge (line 2, stanza 1)

Refracting your image (line 5, stanza 1)

By using rhymes in those two lines, it can be inferred to assume Daud Kamal's intention is to give the poem a musical feel. Other than that it also means that Daud Kamal somehow wants to show the connection of his present with the past memories and its distortion. The bridge symbolizes the connection between the past memories of the poet and his present condition, the depressed feeling of the poet about life.

Graphology is another aspect of style that is examined. The punctuation marks used in the poem are full stops, ellipses, coma, hyphens, and dash. Those punctuation marks show the depressed feeling and thoughts of the poet and at the same time becoming better again with the hope of coming off a good time in life. The grammatical level also contributes to the meaning of the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*”. It is found that Daud Kamal uses the simple present tense in most of the lines with a slight occurrence of the present continuous tense. Depending on when the readers read the poem, the usage of the present tense can be interpreted as a message that the poetry is suitable for anybody at any moment and the continuous process of going into depression and arising with a new hope of a good time in life.

The final stylistic feature is semantic. Four rhetorical strategies were identified by the researcher as contributing to the poem's meaning. The first rhetorical device is symbolism used in the poem by Daud Kamal. According to Wales, a symbol is a sign that is used by the speech community and can be either visual or spoken. (2011, p. 408). The symbols in the poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” is “an ancient bridge”, “flame-mirrors”, “thornbush”, “swelling

rivers”, “thundering horses”, and “rock” etc. The ancient bridge symbolizes the old version and the past memories of the poet about which he is thinking at the present moment. Flame-mirrors symbolize the hope and desire for a better life and thornbush symbolizes the hardships of life in which there still has a deep hope and desire for the coming of good times. Swelling rivers and thundering horses symbolizes the urge for freedom, freedom from those bitter memories and incident and from the bad time in life, and “rock” again symbolizes the hurdles and obstacles of life.

The second rhetorical device found in the poem is imagery. Daud Kamal belongs to the imagists, he was inspired by the great imagist poets, Ezra Pound and W.B. Yeats. The imagery used by the poet in the poem implies the condition and feelings of the poet. The metaphor used in the poem that is leaning on a wall depicts the hope from somewhere or someone from whom we can’t get any kind of help. The next rhetorical device is personification used by the poet in the poem. The personification of swallowing years by the evening mist gives the features of animate objects to the inanimate objects. It shows the sudden and unexpected change in time and in life.

Therefore, it is safe to say that “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” tell us about the hardships and hurdles of life, getting depressed from them and again rising with new hope. Daud Kamal wants readers to realize that whatever depression it is, the time will change and then those cringe memories will become faded.

4.4 The aging process with the passage of time and the sense of nostalgia in “*Erasure*”

Like the first poem “*A Shadow is Not a Memory*” in this poem too the poet Daud Kamal is being nostalgic about the past and speaks about the change in life with the passage of time as the title of the poem “*Erasure*” revealed the main theme of the poem which is erasing, deletion, or cancellation of something. In the poem, the poet describes the phenomenon of aging, with the passage of time everything gets changed and everything needs to change in life. Our wishes and desires get change, it didn’t remain the same as we have in the past. The poem “*Erasure*” has three parts, having three stanzas.

Stanza 1 is about time, as the poet mentioned the word “touch” that symbolizes time and life, that whatever we have in our life we know that it will change soon, so the “touch” can evoke the sense of impermanence and transience of something or someone, expecting the eventual loss of the thing, the person, or the moment that can be both disturbing and sorrowful.

Stanza 2 describes the yearning of the poet for a life that is different from his current reality as the poet mentions the “waterfalls yearning for the impossible”, the waterfalls wishes to be in the depth, something beyond the reach, the desires and wishes of a person. And then, in the very next line, the poet asks a question about love, about loving something or someone, whether it is shadowed by our beliefs and perceptions.

Stanza 3 is about the aging process of a human being and his or her desires and wishes. As time passes, the interest of a man also changes from time to time just like his age. The language features included in the poem, such as phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic features, support the underlying meaning described above.

The poem's phonological elements emphasize the meaning by drawing the reader's focus with the melodic effects created by the consonant and vowel repetition which is alliteration, assonance, and consonance. An example of alliteration is in line 6 of stanza 2;

With what we like to believe?

In this line the consonant sound bilabial /velar voiced glide /w/ is repeated emphasizing the words, and the meaning of the question that the poet asks about love. Here the poet wants to highlight the message he wanted to deliver that whether our idealized notion of love can obscure or distort our understanding of what is truly happening. It shows the complexities of human emotions and perceptions. The assonance /ai/ in line 5 of stanza 4;

I try to salvage

The use of diphthong /ai/ repeatedly in the above line highlights “I” and “try”. Here, the poet, Daud Kamal describes his situation about his nostalgic feeling that he is trying to save and regain those memories, desires, and wishes with his aging body. The consonance used in line 4 of stanza 3 is shown below;

Petals of nostalgia.

Here the consonant sound /t/ highlights the emotions of the poet about his past memories. The poet describes those memories and incidents of his life like the petals of a flower that fell from time to time, just like those petals the old memories become and the new ones take their place, that's why in the last two lines of the poem says that he is trying to save those memories as much as he can.

The second is graphological features found in the poem that deals with punctuation. There are periods, dashes, and question marks in the poem. Full stop/period is the most happens punctuation found in the poem. It depicts the completion of the thoughts of the poet that after longing for the past and yearning for the life change from his present condition, he is still conscious of the present. The dash at the end of the line emphasizes the words and also the sudden change of thoughts. In the poem "*Erasure*" the dashes show the abrupt change in the thoughts of the poet. The question mark shows the complexities of something as the poet ask a question about love and whether it is forgotten and got changed by our beliefs or perception just like in line 5, and 6 of stanza 2"

Is love clouded

With what we like to believe?

In the poem the third feature is tenses. The tense employed in the poem "*Erasure*" is present tense with its two aspects; simple present tense and present continuous tense. The poem's usage of the present tense shows the condition of the poet in the present time, describing the phenomenon of life changes with time, and the phenomenon is continuously happening with everyone at any time in any era describe in lines 1,2 of the stanza 1;

Touch

is the premonition of loss__

In those lines the poet is describing the phenomenon of losing someone or something, a change in the time, passing of the incident, saying that whenever we get something we knew it from the beginning that one day it will be gone.

Last feature found in the poem is semantic features. Imagery, symbols, metaphor, and simile are found in the poem. The imagery used in the poems is in line 3 of stanza 1;

Drift swelling into a tide___

This line is depicting the flow of water that gets changed into the tide, which means that whatever feeling the poet has it is getting more and more intense, a more forceful and overwhelming sensation. The symbol used in the poem is “touch” and “mirror”, the former symbolizes life and time, and the presence of something or someone. The latter symbolizes desires and wishes. The poet says that with touch the feeling of loss came; whatever we have it will be lost one day, and mirrors that symbolize wishes and desires, with the aging of a person, the wishes and desires he/ she has also got old with them and the preferences didn't as same as we have in the past. The metaphor used in the poem is “petals” referring to the memories, the past incidents that become nostalgic for the poet, as Daud Kamal describes in the poem. The simile used in the poem is in line 2 of stanza 3;

Mirrors

Grow old like us. Bleary-eyed.

In these lines the poet is comparing mirrors to the human, that they got features like human beings, just like them they also getting old. Actually, the poet here wants to describe the situation of getting old of the desires and wishes of a person with one's own self.

CHAPTER 5

Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter summarizes the findings of the preceding section's analysis. The purpose of the study is to determine how the language aspects in "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*" are employed, as well as how they contribute to revealing the meaning of each poem. The most important thing is to understand the author's message to the reader, even though every reader will interpret a poem in their own way. After all, the purpose of writing a poem is to convey a specific meaning to the reader. The meaning of the two poems can be attained in this study by investigating the stylistic elements and studying how these elements are employed to construct the poem's meaning.

The study analyzed two poems by Daud Kamal, "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" and "*Erasure*". "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" is a poem that describes the depression and at the same time the hope of the poet, while "*Erasure*", tells about the passing of time, the aging process, and the nostalgic feeling of the poet. Both poems are about past memories, past life, and the present condition of the poet. The first issue, the significance of language aspects in interpreting the content of the poem, is addressed through the use of four stylistic language levels: phonological, graphological, grammatical, and semantic. Both poems contain language elements present at the previously described levels. It has segmental and Supersegmental sound properties on the phonological level. Alliteration, assonance, and consonance are evaluated as segmental features, whereas rhymes in poems are evaluated as Supersegmental features. The poem "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" features para-rhyme, whereas the poem "*Erasure*" does not have any rhyme. The sound effects are used to help convey the meaning of the poems as well as to create an aesthetic effect. On a graphological level, the poet did not follow any defined standards for capitalization and employed a variety of punctuation in both poems. In both poems, two types of tenses are seen at the grammatical level: simple present tense and present continuous tense. The usage of the present tense in the poem reflects the poet's current situation and also implies that the poem is appropriate for anyone at any moment. The last level is the

semantic level, which covered several rhetorical devices such as symbolism, simile, imagery, and metaphor. The rhetorical strategies aid in clarifying the poem's purpose.

The language elements of the poems help reveal the meanings of the poems. The language of "*A Shadow is Not a Memory*" represents the poet's hard times, depression, and desire for a brighter life, whereas the language in "*Erasure*" depicts the aging process with the passing of time and a sense of nostalgia. In both poems, the poet reflects on his former life and on his current positive beliefs. Both poems have the same purpose: they allow Daud Kamal to communicate with people by sharing his experiences and feelings.

Both poems have the same purpose: they allow Daud Kamal to communicate with people by sharing his experiences and feelings. The investigations discussed in Chapter 2 help this study find the language features in the poems.

In conclusion, Daud Kamal, The author of these two poems uses such language qualities to communicate the poem's theme. The study also demonstrates that stylistic analysis can successfully obtain and interpret the poem's message.

❖ **Recommendations**

The researcher would like to recommend the following,

1. Other researchers carry out studies utilizing stylistic analysis in other objects to further improve stylistic analysis. The objects can be other poems by Daud Kamal, Poems from diverse writers, or literary works that have not previously been reviewed.
2. Furthermore, the researcher advises that other researchers increase the scope of the study by expanding the language levels. Because this study only used four language levels, future studies should include more language levels in their analyses. Additional language levels can be used to gain a complete understanding of the poem's meaning

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